

SZ-HB-I-02 Search for a master's program (English)

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Doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10090628
ID	SZ-HB-I-02
Title	Search for a master's program
Educational area	#higher-education
Persona	P: Nadine - Student https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13951710
Short description	Nadine is in the final stages of her bachelor's degree and would like to find a suitable master's programme.
Result	Nadine finds a suitable master's programme with the help of the LearningPathFinder.
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Process "Search for interest tests"
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Nadine is registered at BIRD• Nadine is logged in to BIRD
Components	#learningpathfinder #profile #chat #workspace #data-wallet
Services / tools	uni-assist e. V.

Problem scenario

Introduction

Nadine Kasoevi is studying Educational Science and Mathematics at the University of Vechta. She is in her eighth semester the final stages of her bachelor's degree. During her studies, it has become clear that biology, nature conservation and environmental protection are particularly important to her. Nadine plans to pursue a master's degree and would prefer to start immediately after her Bachelor.

problem definition

Nadine is looking for suitable degree programs that combine all her interests. Location is not a decisive factor for her. She is willing to relocate in order to study her desired subject. She is aware that biology, nature conservation and environmental protection are

related fields, but finding a master's program that equally combines all of them is not easy. It is also important to her that she settles in quickly at her new university, which is why Nadine pays attention to the available extracurricular activities as well.

Background and context

Nadine is about to complete her bachelor's degree and would like to start a master's program. During her year of voluntary service in Kenya, she witnessed the effects of climate change on people's lives, and she is noticing these effects in Germany as well. Environmental issues are very close to her heart, and she hopes to work in this field in the future. As she is currently studying Education and Mathematics, she wants to take a different direction in her master's degree in order to get closer to her dream job.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

Nadine knows what her interests are, but she does not yet have any in-depth knowledge in this area. It is therefore difficult for her to assess which degree programs could combine all her interests and ultimately be the right choice for her.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

Nadine has already tried searching online to find out which master's programs are offered in the fields of biology, nature conservation and environmental protection. However, since she rarely uses the internet, she mainly relies on the digital resources provided by her university. She feels unsettled by the seemingly vague results of her search and would like to be able to navigate relevant search results quickly and easily.

Activity scenario

Process "Search for interest tests"

Step 1: Nadine opens BIRD.

Step 2: Nadine uses the LearningPathFinder to search for information about a potential master's program. She would like to find out more about the following topics:

- Contact details for the University of Potsdam
- Available programs
- Admission requirements
- Study regulations

Step 3: Nadine updates her data in the Data-Wallet and agrees to share it with the LearningPathFinder, which can then respond more specifically to Nadine's current situation.

Step 4: Based on her preferences and qualifications, Nadine is only shown study-

related topics. She decides to take an interest test and then find out about various degree programmes at the University of Potsdam. She also registers with uni-assist e. V.

Step 5: She logs in to uni-assist e. V. using single sign-on and navigates to the website.

Step 6: She is offered various topic program and information pages. Nadine manually selects her learning path through the pages.

Step 7: After completing the test, Nadine saves the results in her Data-Wallet

Step 8: She returns to BIRD and continues her original search to find out more about the University of Potsdam, its admission requirements and study regulations.

Step 9: Since everything aligns with her goals, Nadine finally decides to apply to the University of Potsdam via uni-assist e. V. to pursue her desired master's degree.